

“Open access allows for multimedia work in a different way. I couldn't imagine publishing this work in a more traditional format.”

Francesca Coppa, Professor
of English, Theatre and Film
Studies at Muhlenberg College

Open access publishing is rooted in the digital age. As a result, Coppa says it encourages innovation, such as new ways of creating and producing research. It enables academics to play around with form and content and to make the most of digital publishing. This suits Coppa, who is a strong advocate of remix cultures and transmedia storytelling. Her research explores how stories overlap across text, video, theatre and image, so it was essential when she published her latest book that the output included and reflected the actual research.

Coppa said: “It's a book about video artists, so it was really important to me to include clips and examples of the art.”

How open access publishing benefitted Coppa's research

It supported experimentation around form, content and style

It is multimedia, enabling Coppa to include videos, clips, images and links connected to the research

The research output was designed to suit the research material and message